

The effect of family capital on students' career maturity

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. College students are in the stage of career exploration, and some of them lack sufficient knowledge of their own majors and abilities, and lack long-term career planning in terms of employment choice. The family's background in economic, cultural and social aspects affects the individual's choice of profession, which in turn correlates with the students' career maturity. Therefore, this study examines the influencing factors of career maturity from the perspective of family capital, which can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the role of the family in the individual's career development.

Study participants and methods. In this study, students majoring in painting at three fine arts colleges in Liaoning Province will be selected as the research subjects of this study. A total of 880 official questionnaires of this study were recovered, and after deleting the invalid questionnaires with too short a response time and too much repetitiveness of answers, 816 valid questionnaires were retained, with an effective recovery rate of 92.73%. This study uses the research method of questionnaire survey method.

Results. The results of t-test analysis of family capital by gender show that the t-value is 0.456 which is not significant ($p > .05$), indicating that there is no significant difference between the students' "gender" in terms of family capital; and the results of t-test analysis of vocational maturity by gender show that the t-value is 1.401 which is not significant ($p > .05$). The results of one-way ANOVA analysis of family capital by grade showed that the F-value was 0.526 which was not significant ($p > .05$), indicating that there was no significant difference in family capital by 'grade' of the students; the results of one-way ANOVA analysis of vocational maturity by grade showed that the F-value was 1.202 which was not significant ($p > .05$). The results of t-test analysis of family capital by place of origin show that the t-value of 14.195 reaches the significant level ($p < .001$), indicating that there is a significant difference in family capital by students' "place of origin". The result of t-test analysis of career maturity by place of origin shows that the t-value is 14.156 which is significant ($p < .001$) and indicates that there is a significant difference in career maturity by 'place of origin' of students. Family capital ($\beta = .719$, $p < .001$) was a significant positive predictor of career maturity, indicating that the higher the students' family capital, the higher their career maturity.

Conclusion. In this study, through the questionnaire method, the influence of Family Capital on career maturity was systematically analyzed, and the roles of Family Economic Capital, Family Cultural Capital, and Family Social Capital in the development of students' career maturity were verified. Through this comprehensive analysis, the study not only deepens the understanding of career maturity but also provides a solid theoretical foundation for further exploring the differences in career development and social mobility among different social classes in the future.

KEYWORDS

family capital, social capital, stratification theory, career development, career maturity

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a surge in the number of college graduates and great competitive pressure. College students are in the stage of career exploration, and some of them suffer from shallow career cognition, lack of practical ability, unclear motivation for choosing a career, lack of sufficient knowledge of their profession and ability, and lack of long-term career planning in employment choice [1]. Family capital plays an important role in the career maturity of painting students, influencing not only career choice and career orientation but also performance and development in their careers [2]. Families with rich cultural capital provide painting majors with a wider range of learning opportunities and diverse artistic experiences, and by fostering a strong interest in the arts from an early age, students are more likely to clarify their career direction and feel more confident in their career choices [3]. At the same time, family capital provides more financial support for painting majors, enabling students to participate in more art projects and exhibitions, and to enhance their professionalism and visibility, making family capital conducive for painting majors to obtain more opportunities and resources in their careers [4]. In the family environment, there is a need for someone to encourage and support a child's artistic talent and endeavors, which can help the child to overcome obstacles, consistently pursue his or her career goals, and achieve success and maturity in the profession [5]. It has been shown that there are differences in family capital and career maturity by gender, grade level, and place of origin, respectively; however, research on the factors influencing career maturity usually involves only a generalized consideration of the family aspect, rather than an in-depth exploration from a comprehensive perspective of family capital [6; 7]. By examining the impact of family capital on the career maturity of painting students, it is possible to better understand how the family environment shapes one's performance and achievement in the career field. Improving the relevance of educational and career development policies can help policymakers develop more targeted educational and career development policies. Policies can balance career development opportunities by providing more educational resources and financial support to help students who lack family capital [8].

Family capital plays an important role in the career maturity of students majoring in painting, which lays the foundation for students' career development, enhances students' competitiveness and career stability, and helps students to grow and succeed in their career. To study the influencing factors of career maturity from the perspective of family capital, we can have a more comprehensive understanding of the role of family in individual career development. Therefore, in future studies, more attention and in-depth exploration of the impact of family capital on career maturity will help to provide more specific and detailed research results.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Theoretical Foundations

Career development theory emerged in the 1950s and was specifically applied to the practice of career guidance in the 1960s and 1970s. Its main representative is the American vocational guidance expert Super [9], and later, based on Ginzberg and Reilley's research, it further developed and put forward its career life stage theory, and gradually formed a theoretical system [10]. This theory explores the process of career choice from a developmental point of view and studies individual career behavior, career development stages, and career maturity, thus becoming an important theoretical doctrine in the field of Western career guidance. Career development theory emphasizes the influence of individuals' developmental stages and psychological traits on career decision-making in their careers, which helps to explore in depth the formation process and key factors of students' career maturity, and provides theoretical support for the development of individualized career development strategies.

Social stratification theory focuses on the distribution of status and opportunities for individuals in society. Individuals in society are categorized into different classes or levels based on their family background, education, economic status, etc., and there is social mobility between the levels,

which means that individuals can change their social status through effort and opportunity [11]. The social stratification theory can help this study understand the impact of family capital on the career maturity of painting majors at the Liaoning Fine Arts Institute in China, and examine the opportunities and challenges of students from different backgrounds in their career development. Meanwhile, the career development theory emphasizes the influence of individuals' developmental stages and psychological traits on career decision-making in their careers, which can help to explore the formation process and key factors of students' career maturity in-depth and provide theoretical support for the development of personalized career development strategies.

2. Family Capital

In Marx's *Capital*, capital is recognized as the value that brings surplus value, and it is not a pure object but carries certain economic, property, and social relations [12]. How individuals make behavioral decisions and their corresponding outcomes are influenced to some extent by resource endowments, which are manifested in the rational choices individuals make based on resources in response to uncertain external environments. Barney argues that a composite measure of indicators such as family income, education, occupation, and social relationships can be referred to as Family Capital and Bourdieu discusses Family Social Capital by categorizing it into three categories: economic capital, social capital, and cultural capital [13].

Bourdieu identified Family Capital as a key indispensable element for personal growth and success, which directly influences a person's learning experience in school as well as his/her material standard of living in daily life [14]. With sufficient economic capital, families can provide better educational resources and learning environments for their children to have more learning opportunities and quality education [15]. Cheng and Kaplowitz stated that the Family Capital of culture has three forms: objectification, institutionalization, and embodiment, and that this diversity depends largely on capital's key operational mechanisms [16]. Dumais suggests that Family Capital exhibits implicit characteristics, which are specifically categorized into several dimensions, including dimensions such as the amount of educational resources and the frequency of borrowing books [17]. In addition, differences in social networks, which act as a bridge between the family and external resources, also play a role in family support, with families of higher socio-economic status often being able to connect with more influential people and have access to a wider range of resources and opportunities [18].

The three sub-dimensions of Family Capital are not completely independent from each other, and all three interact with each other and cross-influence each other [19]. Having higher Family Capital leads to better Family Cultural Capital, as economically affluent families are more able to provide cultural activities and learning resources. In turn, good Family Capital promotes the development of social capital among family members, as active participation in cultural activities and education contributes to a wider social circle and relationships.

3. Career Maturity

Super originally defined vocational maturity as "the position reached on the continuum of vocational development from exploration to decline", emphasizing that the more vocationally mature a person is, the more he or she behaves vocationally like an older person at the same stage of life (e.g., adolescence) [20]. In the subsequent years of continuous research, Super supplemented and expanded the connotation of career maturity and redefined the concept of career maturity, which is considered to be the degree to which an individual accomplishes the corresponding developmental tasks in his or her life stage, and categorized career maturity into the following basic dimensions: career choice orientation, career information, career planning, career traits, and career preferences [21]. Individual career maturity is the level of development of an individual in these five basic dimensions during his or her career development stage.

Super in his theory of career development states that career maturity is the degree to which an individual accomplishes the occupational tasks appropriate to his stage of development [21]. Vocational maturity is the level of development of vocational behaviors appropriate to an individual's age, i. e., the level at which an individual meets societal expectations throughout his or her career, and can be measured in terms of developmental tasks at various stages of

development. As can be seen from the explanation of the concept of career maturity, the theory of career maturity at this point is closely linked and complementary to the theory of career development. Levinson et al. consider an individual's career maturity as an ability, i.e., the individual's awareness and ability to make career decisions that meet the requirements of reality in a certain situation, and this ability maintains its consistency and stability at a certain time [22]. Adopting Hart's research perspective, this study defines career maturity as a comprehensive concept that encompasses multiple aspects of an individual's career, including clarity of career goals, knowledge of and confidence in one's career competence and value, autonomy over career choices, the influence of family and social relationships on career decision-making, and the ability to accept and draw on career references and role models [23]. It also provides a more in-depth and comprehensive perspective on students' career maturity by enabling a comprehensive understanding of the development and growth process of individuals in their careers.

Lareau and Weininger's study shows that families with a high level of cultural capital are often characterized by a greater emphasis on the development of competence, self-confidence, and autonomy in the transmission of cultural capital by the parents [24]. Parents emphasize the incorporation of modern cultural factors and encourage their children to be exposed to a diversity of knowledge and experiences to develop their children's competitiveness and resilience in the modern world. Yang et al. conducted a study on college students' career maturity, career values, and career choices upon graduation [25]. The results of their study revealed the influence of college students with different levels of career maturity on career decision-making, including choices in terms of salary expectations and place of employment.

4. Correlation Studies Between Variables

In a related study with gender as a background variable, Brulé and Gaikwad emphasized that there are significant differences at the gender level in the Family Capital of university students [26]. The female group showed greater differences in the level of Family Capital, social, and cultural capital, highlighting the more significant differences in the level of Family Capital, social, and cultural capital of the individual females in the study population. Luzzo used the Attitude Scale in his study on the career maturity and career development of students [27]. In a related study using gender as a background variable, Brulé and Gaikwad emphasized that there are significant differences in the Family Capital of university students at the gender level [26]. The female group showed greater differences in the level of Family Capital, Social, and Cultural Capital, highlighting the more significant differences in the level of Family Capital, Social, and Cultural Capital of the individual females in the study population. Luzzo used the Attitude Scale in his study, which explored the career maturity and career development of students [27]. The results of the study showed that women were significantly more aware of career maturity attitude scores than men. In addition, females were also more aware of role conflict and career development barriers, and in comparison, females showed more career planning. Therefore, combining the insights from the above studies, this study proposes H1: There are significant differences in family capital and career maturity among painting students of different genders in Liaoning Province, China.

In a related study using grade level as a background variable, Mi et al. on Family Capital stated that there are significant differences in Family Capital among college students of different grades [28]. Fourth-grade college students have the highest levels of Family Economic Capital, Family Social Capital, and Family Cultural Capital. He and Guo pointed out that in terms of changes in grade development, the level of career maturity of high school students increases as they move up the grades [29]. Therefore, combining the insights from the above studies, this study proposes H2: There are significant differences in family capital and career maturity among painting students in Liaoning Province, China.

In a related study with birthplace as the background variable, Liu and Zhao take Family Economic Capital, Family Cultural Capital, and Family Social Capital as the entry point, revealing that rural Family Capital lags significantly behind urban family capital in all aspects [30]. Based on this finding, a government-led approach is proposed to improve rural family capital to combat poverty in rural areas. Lau et al.'s study found that there is a significant difference between urban and rural areas in the career maturity of college students [31]. Therefore, combining the ideas from the above studies,

this study proposes H3: There are significant differences in family capital and career maturity among different places of origin painting students in Liaoning Province, China.

Regarding the impact of Family Capital on career maturity, studies have shown that a high level of family social capital provides students with more high-quality references, and excellent role models around them can play a leading role in stimulating individuals' motivation to continue to learn from experience and knowledge [32]. Families tend to have open-minded qualities, adopt good educational practices, and provide scientific guidance and spiritual care for their children, enabling them to express their ideas and aspirations more rationally, clarify their future career plans, and be confident about future career challenges [33]. Therefore, this study proposes H4: There is a significant positive effect of family capital on the career maturity of painting students in Liaoning Province, China.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DESIGN

The framework of this study contains two variables, namely Family Capital and Career Maturity. Family Capital is categorized into three dimensions, i.e., Family Economic Capital, Family Cultural Capital, and Family Social Capital; and Career Maturity is categorized into six dimensions, i.e., Career Goal, Career Self-confidence, Career Value, Career Autonomy, Reliance on Family and Friends, and Career Reference. The research framework also includes three background variables: gender, grade level, and place of origin. A diagram of the specific research framework is shown below:

Figure 1 Research Framework Diagram

1. Research Subjects

In this study, students majoring in painting at three fine arts colleges in Liaoning Province will be selected as the research subjects of this study. Fine arts colleges focus on cultivating students' professional skills in art creation, design, and expression. In terms of educational resources, fine arts colleges are richer in the field of art. They usually have more specialized art teachers and facilities, such as specialized laboratories and studios for painting, sculpture, photography, etc., which enable students to study and practice art creation in greater depth. In terms of academic atmosphere, fine arts colleges usually focus on cultivating academic research and creative abilities. Students are more likely to be exposed to academic content such as art theories and aesthetic studies within art schools so that they can better understand and grasp the meaning and significance of art. This study was conducted through an online electronic questionnaire distribution. For the credibility of the questionnaire, a total of 230 pre-test questionnaires were distributed for analysis in this study, and the credibility of the measurement results was tested through the reliability of the selected scales (internal consistency test), and the validity of the selected scales (validated factor analysis) was tested for validity as a means of examining the degree of accuracy and adaptability of the

questionnaire design. A total of 880 official questionnaires of this study were recovered, and after deleting the invalid questionnaires with too short a response time and too much repetitiveness of answers, 816 valid questionnaires were retained, with an effective recovery rate of 92.73%. To achieve the validity of the questionnaire data, the QR code of the questionnaire of the study was distributed to the student management department of each university and transferred to the class group by the corresponding counselor to supervise and prompt please fill out the answer in strict accordance with the instructions of the project information, and the questionnaires were completed within 10 days of recovery.

2. Research Methodology

This study uses the research method of questionnaire survey method, which has several advantages in social science research in terms of its ability to quickly obtain data from a large number of samples, thus providing a comprehensive understanding of the opinions, attitudes, and behaviors of the group [34]. At the same time, questionnaires facilitate the unification and standardization of the data collection process, avoiding subjectivity and non-consistency caused by methods such as face-to-face interviews [35]. The data generated from questionnaires are relatively convenient to be counted and analyze, helping researchers to extract valuable information and conclusions from large amounts of data [36].

3. Research Instrument

The Family Capital Scale developed by Buchmann was used in this study [37]. The scale consists of three dimensions: Family Economic Capital, Family Cultural Capital, and Family Social Capital, with a total of 42 items. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 are for Family Economic Capital, 7-19 are for Family Cultural Capital, and 20-42 are for Family Social Capital, with the 18th item being a reversed item. The scale is rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 to 5 as "Very Inconsistent," "Relatively Inconsistent," "Difficult to Determine," "Comparatively Consistent" and "Very Consistent".

In the pretest analysis, the Family Capital Scale was analyzed by item analysis, and the retained items were analyzed for reliability, and the results showed that the overall Cronbach's Alpha value of the scale was .968, which indicated that the Family Capital Scale had good reliability. In addition, the retained items were subjected to exploratory factor analysis to analyze the consistency of the factor structure of the scale with the theory. The results showed that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value was .963, the Bartlett spherical test value was 7081.710 ($p=0.000$), and the factor loadings of each item ranged from .717-.833, with a cumulative total explained variance of 66.517% for the three dimensions, indicating that the Family Capital Scale had good construct validity in this study.

In the formal questionnaire reliability analysis, the overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the Family Capital scale was .971, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient meets the criterion of being greater than .700, which indicates that the reliability of the Family Capital scale is good. The absolute fit of the model: $\chi^2/df= 2.207$, GFI= 0.907, AGFI= 0.897, RMSEA= 0.038, SRMR= 0.030; the value-added fit: NFI= 0.938, NNFI= 0.963, IFI= 0.965, CFI= 0.965; the streamlined fit: PNFI= 0.889, PGFI= 0.820. All of the fit indicators met the judgmental standardized values or higher, indicating a good fit for Family Capital. Standardized factor loadings ranged from .756 - .833, all of which were greater than the judgmental value of .400, indicating a good measurement relationship. Squared Multiple Correlations (SMC) values ranged from .571 - .683, all greater than the judgmental criterion of .500. Combined Reliability CR values ranged from .908 - .976, all greater than the judgmental value of .600, and Squared Variance Extracted (AVE) values ranged from .621 - .641, all greater than the judgmental value of .400, suggesting that the data have good convergent validity.

This study utilized the revised Student Career Maturity Scale by Zhang et al. [38]. The scale was revised from the Korean version of the Student Career Maturity Scale. The scale contains six dimensions of career goals, career self-confidence, career value, career autonomy, family and friend dependence, and career reference, totaling 34 items. The eight items of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 are for career goals, the six items of 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14 are for career self-confidence, the six items of 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, and 20 are for career value, the four items of 21, 22, 23, and 24 are for

career autonomy, the four items of 25, 26, 27, and 28 are for dependence on friends and family, and the 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, and 34 six items for career reference, where the items for the dimensions of career self-confidence and career value were reversed. The scale is rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 to 5 as "Very Inconsistent," "Relatively Inconsistent," "Difficult to Determine," "Comparatively Consistent" and "Very Consistent".

In the pretest analysis, the items of the students' career maturity scale were analyzed and the retained items were analyzed for reliability, and the results showed that the overall Cronbach's alpha of the scale was .935, which indicated that the student's career maturity scale had a good level of reliability. In addition, the retained items were subjected to exploratory factor analysis to analyze the factor structure of the scale by the theory. The results showed that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value was .963, the Bartlett spherical test value was 4193.551 ($p=0.000$), the factor loadings for each item ranged from .707-.821, and the cumulative total explained variance for the six-dimensional factors was 68.857%, which indicated that the Students' Career Maturity Scale had good construct validity for the measurement of the present study. In the formal questionnaire reliability analysis, the overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the Career Maturity Scale was .940, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient complied with the criterion of being greater than .700, which indicated that the reliability of the Student Career Maturity Scale was good. The absolute fit of the model: $\chi^2/df=2.392$, GFI= 0.921, AGFI= 0.908, RMSEA= 0.041, SRMR= 0.032; the value-added fit: NFI= 0.935, NNFI= 0.957, IFI= 0.961, CFI= 0.961; the streamlined fit: PNFI= 0.853, PGFI= 0.792. All of the fit indicators were above the judgmental standardized values, indicating a good fit for occupational maturity. Standardized factor loadings ranged from .751 - .835, all greater than the judgmental value of .400, indicating a good measurement relationship. Squared Multiple Correlations (SMC) values ranged from .563 - .698, all greater than the judgmental criterion of .500. Combined Reliability CR values ranged from .874 - .976, all greater than the judgmental value of .600, and Squared Variance Extracted (AVE) values ranged from .612 - .648, all greater than the judgmental value of .400, suggesting that there is good convergent validity of the data.

Since the Family Capital Scale and the Career Maturity Scale were filled out simultaneously in this study, the subjects might have analogization problems during the process of filling out the responses and thus have an impact on the results of the study, so a common method variability test was needed. The KMO value for this test was .967, which was greater than the reference value of .800, and Bartlett's Sphericity Test reached significance ($p= .000$), which fulfills the criteria for the common method test of variability. The unrotated exploratory factor analysis results extracted a total of nine factors with eigenroots greater than 1, and the maximum factor variance explained was 36.120% (less than 40%), so there was no serious common method bias, and thus the next step of the analysis could be carried out.

ANALYSIS OF STUDY RESULTS

1. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

In the formal research sample, the background variables of college students majoring in painting at the Fine Arts Academy of Liaoning Province, China, contained: gender, grade level, and place of origin. In terms of gender, 332 (40.70%) were male students and 484 (59.30%) were female students, which was a relatively even proportion. In terms of grade, 196 (24.00%) were freshmen, 228 (27.90%) were sophomores, 232 (28.40%) were juniors and 160 (19.60%) were seniors, with more sophomores and juniors. In terms of place of origin, 488 (59.80%) were from towns and 328 (40.20%) were from villages, which is a relatively equal percentage.

The Family Capital Scale contains three dimensions, Family Economic Capital, Family Cultural Capital, and Family Social Capital, and the situation is analyzed by mean and standard deviation, which are 3.341 and 0.815. The Family Capital Scale is a 5-point scale, where higher scores indicate higher family capital, with a theoretical median of 3. Thus the mean of this study is in the upper middle level. The family Capital dimension mean is 3.287 and the standard deviation is 0.963 which is in the upper middle level. The family Capital dimension mean is 3.335 with a standard deviation

of 0.981 which is in the upper middle level. The mean of the Family Capital dimension is 3.359, with a standard deviation of 0.990, which is at the upper middle level. From the results, the family capital dimensions of college students majoring in painting at Liaoning Fine Arts Institute in China are prioritized in the order of Family Social Capital, Family Cultural Capital, and Family Economic Capital.

The Career Maturity Scale contains six dimensions career goals, career confidence, career value, career autonomy, family and friends dependence, and career reference, and the situation was analyzed by mean and standard deviation, which was 3.360 with a standard deviation of 0.696. The career maturity scale is a 5-point scale, and the higher the score indicates the higher the degree of career maturity, with the theoretical median of 3. Therefore the mean of the present study is in the middle to upper level. The Career Goals dimension has a mean of 3.373 with a standard deviation of 0.996, which is in the upper middle range. The mean of the Career Confidence dimension is 3.365 with a standard deviation of 1.009, which is in the upper-middle range. The mean of the Career Values dimension is 3.383 with a standard deviation of 0.971, which is in the upper-middle level. The mean of the career autonomy dimension is 3.388 with a standard deviation of 1.027, which is in the upper middle level. The mean of the family and friends dependency dimension is 3.367 with a standard deviation of 1.035, which is in the upper middle level. The mean of the career reference dimension is 3.357 with a standard deviation of 1.011, which is at the upper middle level. From the results, college students majoring in painting at the Liaoning Fine Arts Institute in China prioritized the dimensions of career maturity as career autonomy, career value, career goal, family and friend dependence, career self-confidence, and career reference in the order of priority.

2. Analysis of Differences

To test whether there are significant differences between different genders of Chinese college students majoring in painting at Liaoning Fine Arts College on each variable, this study used an independent sample t-test to conduct the analysis.

The results of t-test analysis of Family Capital of different genders showed that the t-value was .456, which did not reach the significant level ($p > .05$), indicating that there was no significant difference in Family Capital of different genders of college students majoring in painting in Liaoning Fine Arts Institute of China.

The results of t-test analysis of vocational maturity of different genders show that the t-value of vocational self-confidence dimension of vocational maturity is 2.662, which reaches the significant level ($p < .01$), indicating that there is a significant difference in vocational self-confidence dimension of college students majoring in painting in Liaoning Fine Arts College of China between different genders, among which, male students (Mean 3.487) are larger than female students (Mean 3.287), so it indicates that male students have more vocational self-confidence than female students in their vocational capital. career self-confidence is higher than that of female students. The t-value of the vocational autonomy dimension in vocational maturity is 2.684, which reaches a significant level ($p < .01$), indicating that there is a significant difference in vocational autonomy dimension between different genders of college students majoring in painting in Liaoning Fine Arts College of China, in which the male students (Mean 3.505) are greater than the female students (Mean 3.309), thus suggesting that male students are more autonomous than female students in their vocational autonomy.

To test whether there are significant differences in the variables among college students majoring in painting at Liaoning Fine Arts College of China in different grades, the present study used one-way ANOVA analysis and post hoc multiple comparisons to analyze the results.

The results of one-way ANOVA analysis on Family Capital showed that the F-value of .526 did not reach the significant level ($p > .05$), indicating that there is no significant difference in Family Capital among college students majoring in painting at Liaoning Fine Arts College in China.

The results of the one-way ANOVA analysis of career maturity in different grades showed that the F-value of the career value dimension of career maturity was 3.050, which reached the significant level ($p < .05$), indicating that there was a significant difference between different grades of college students majoring in painting at Liaoning Fine Arts College in China in the dimension of career value. Post hoc comparisons were made using Scheffe's method because of the homogeneity of the variances.

The sophomore (Mean 3.480) was greater than the junior (Mean 3.226), thus indicating that the sophomore students had higher career value than the juniors. The F-value of the career reference dimension of career maturity was 2.833, which reached the significant level ($p < .05$), indicating that there were significant differences in the career reference dimension among college students majoring in painting at Liaoning Fine Arts College in China in different grades. Post hoc comparisons were made using Scheffe's method because of the homogeneity of the number of variants. The freshman year (Mean 3.527) was greater than the senior year (Mean 3.235), thus indicating that the freshman year students were higher in career reference than the senior year students.

Table 1

Table analyzing the differences in each variable among college students majoring in painting at the Academy of Fine Arts by gender (n=816)

Test Variable	Gender	M	SD	t	p	Comparison of Differences
Family Capital	Male	3.357	0.825	.456	.648	----
	Female	3.330	0.809			
Family Economic Capital	Male	3.306	0.960	.478	.633	----
	Female	3.273	0.966			
Family Cultural Capital	Male	3.409	0.975	1.795	.073	----
	Female	3.284	0.983			
Family Social Capital	Male	3.340	1.001	.439	.661	----
	Female	3.371	0.983			
Career Maturity	Male	3.401	0.680	1.401	.161	----
	Female	3.332	0.706			
Career Goals	Male	3.370	0.944	.057	.954	----
	Female	3.374	1.031			
Career Confidence	Male	3.478	0.995	2.662	.008	Male > Female
	Female	3.287	1.013			
Career Values	Male	3.395	0.975	.278	.781	----
	Female	3.375	0.970			
Career Autonomy	Male	3.505	1.023	2.684	.007	Male > Female
	Female	3.309	1.022			
Reliance on family and friends	Male	3.298	0.992	.719	.473	----
	Female	3.246	1.063			
Career Reference	Male	3.371	0.995	.329	.743	----
	Female	3.348	1.023			

Table 2

Table analyzing the differences in Family Capital among college students majoring in painting at different grade of the College of Fine Arts (n=816)

Test Variable	Grade	M	SD	F	p	Comparison of Differences
Family Capital	1	3.317	0.855	.526	.664	----
	2	3.369	0.792			
	3	3.373	0.824			
	4	3.284	0.789			

Family Economic Capital	1	3.286	0.932	.498	.683	----
	2	3.227	1.054			
	3	3.333	0.922			
	4	3.306	0.925			
Family Cultural Capital	1	3.367	0.972	.603	.613	----
	2	3.306	1.001			
	3	3.384	0.975			
	4	3.264	0.976			
Family Social Capital	1	3.296	1.057	1.092	.352	----
	2	3.442	0.926			
	3	3.377	1.023			
	4	3.290	0.942			

Table 3

Table analyzing the differences in Career Maturity among college students majoring in painting at different grade of the College of Fine Arts (n=816)

Test Variable	Grade	M	SD	F	p	Comparison of Differences
Career Maturity	1	3.434	0.683	1.202	.308	----
	2	3.367	0.705			
	3	3.320	0.714			
	4	3.317	0.670			
Career Goals	1	3.403	0.959	.175	.913	----
	2	3.341	1.035			
	3	3.390	0.993			
	4	3.356	0.995			
Career Confidence	1	3.446	1.026	1.481	.218	----
	2	3.395	1.009			
	3	3.362	0.976			
	4	3.227	1.032			
Career Values	1	3.439	1.016	3.050	.028	2 > 3
	2	3.480	0.962			
	3	3.226	1.001			
	4	3.406	0.862			
Career Autonomy	1	3.357	1.061	.200	.897	----
	2	3.401	0.960			
	3	3.422	1.043			
	4	3.359	1.059			
Reliance on family and friends	1	3.406	1.042	2.196	.087	----
	2	3.206	0.990			
	3	3.175	1.038			
	4	3.319	1.070			
Career Reference	1	3.527	0.950	2.833	.037	1 > 4
	2	3.348	1.036			
	3	3.307	0.985			
	4	3.235	1.066			

To test whether there is a significant difference in each variable among college students majoring in painting at the Liaoning Fine Arts Institute of China in different places of origin, this study used an independent samples t-test to conduct the analysis.

The results of the t-test analysis of Family Capital in different places of origin show that the t-value of 14.195 reaches the significant level ($p < .001$), indicating that there is a significant difference in the overall Family Capital of the college students majoring in painting in Liaoning Fine Arts College of China in different places of origin. The urban (Mean 3.622) is greater than the rural (Mean 2.923), thus indicating that students with urban have higher Family Capital than those with rural.

The results of the t-test analysis of career maturity in different places of origin showed that the t-value of 14.156 reached the significant level ($p < .001$), indicating that there is a significant difference in career maturity among college students majoring in painting in Liaoning Fine Arts College in China in different places of origin as a whole. The urban (Mean 3.601) is greater than the rural (Mean 3.002), thus indicating that students with urban household registration are more mature than those with rural household registration. The t-value of 10.874 for the career goal dimension of career maturity reaches a significant level ($p < .001$), indicating that there are significant differences in the career goal dimension among college students majoring in painting at Liaoning Fine Arts College in China with different places of origin.

Table 4

Table analyzing the differences in each variable among college students majoring in painting at art colleges in different places of origin (n=816)

Test Variable	Birthplace	M	SD	t	p	Comparison of Differences
Family Capital	Towns	3.622	0.832	14.195	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	2.923	0.575			
Family Economic Capital	Towns	3.466	0.972	6.769	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	3.020	0.887			
Family Cultural Capital	Towns	3.589	1.003	9.897	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	2.957	0.814			
Family Social Capital	Towns	3.682	0.976	12.893	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	2.878	0.797			
Career Maturity	Towns	3.601	0.705	14.156	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	3.002	0.503			
Career Goals	Towns	3.663	0.953	10.874	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	2.941	0.898			
Career Confidence	Towns	3.543	1.016	6.394	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	3.100	0.940			
Career Values	Towns	3.610	0.946	8.481	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	3.046	0.909			
Career Autonomy	Towns	3.627	1.026	8.621	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	3.034	0.920			
Reliance on family and friends	Towns	3.511	1.011	8.580	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	2.904	0.962			
Career Reference	Towns	3.607	1.019	9.264	.000	Towns > Rural
	Rural	2.987	0.877			

3. Correlation Analysis

In this study, to understand the correlation between Family Capital and students' career maturity in Liaoning Province, China, Pearson correlation analysis was used to analyze the correlation between Family Capital and students' career degree. Correlation analysis is mainly to study the correlation between variables, the value of the correlation coefficient ranges between -1 - 1, the larger the absolute value of r , the stronger the correlation between variables. The absolute value of the correlation coefficient is high when it is .700 - .990, medium, when it is .400 - .690, low when it is .100 - .390, and a value of .100 or less, which indicates that there is no correlation between the variables. The correlation coefficient between Family Capital and Career Maturity in the current study was .668, which is less than .800 therefore there is no problem of covariance [39]. Family Capital is moderately positively correlated with career maturity ($r=.668$, $p<.001$) indicating that the better the Family Capital the higher the career maturity of the students.

Table 5

Table of results of correlation analysis of research variables

Variable	M	SD	Family Capital	Career Maturity
Family Capital	3.341	0.815	1	
Career Maturity	3.360	0.696	.668***	1

4. Regression Analysis

This study establishes a model of the influence of Family Capital on students' career maturity. Validated factor analysis was conducted to evaluate the model's fitness in terms of the model's absolute fitness, value-added fitness, and the model's streamlined fitness. The results show that χ^2/df is less than 3, and less than the reference value of 5 means that the model fitness is high. The results of the validation factor analysis in this study showed that the absolute fit of the model: $\chi^2/df = 2.304$, GFI = 0.841, AGFI = 0.832, RMSEA = 0.040, SRMR = 0.035; value-added fit: NFI = 0.878, NNFI = 0.925, IFI = 0.927, CFI = 0.927; streamlined fit: PNFI = 0.852, PGFI = 0.794. All the fit indicators met the criteria for judgment and could be analyzed in regression. fitness: PNFI = 0.852, PGFI = 0.794; each fitting index reaches above the judgment standard value, meets the model fitness standard, and can be analyzed by regression.

In the regression analysis, the influence relationship was tested using linear regression analysis to test the hypotheses with Family Capital as the independent variable and occupational maturity as the dependent variable. In terms of the covariance problem, the variance inflation factor VIF values are all below 10, indicating that there is no covariance problem between the variables, and the next step of analysis can be carried out.

In Model 1 of this study, the predictive effect of background variables on career maturity was tested by regression analysis after controlling for students' gender, grade, and place of origin, and the results of the data analysis showed that the R^2 value was 0.187, which indicated that different genders, grades, and places of origin of the students majoring in painting in the Academy of Fine Arts in Liaoning Province, China, explained 18.7% of the career maturity.

In Model 2 of this study, after controlling for students' gender, grade, and place of origin, the predictive effect of background variables and Family Capital on career maturity was tested by regression analysis, and Family Capital ($\beta= 0.719$, $p< 0.001$) had a significant positive predictive effect on career maturity, indicating that the higher the students' Family Capital, the higher their career maturity. Thus, H4 of this study: a significant positive effect of Family Capital on career maturity of students majoring in Painting at Liaoning Fine Arts College, China, is established.

Table 6

Table of Results of Regression Analysis of Family Capital and Career Maturity

Variable	Model I		Model II	
	Career Maturity		Career Maturity	
	Beta	t	Beta	t
Control Variable				
Male	0.059	1.850	0.040	1.822
Freshman	0.094	2.262*	0.068	2.373*
Sophomore	0.043	1.033	0.005	0.156
Junior	0.027	0.631	-0.024	-0.815
Town	0.424	13.379***	0.121	4.969***
Dependent Variable				
Family Capital			0.719	29.618***
F-value	37.219		210.771	
R ²	0.187		0.610	
ΔR ²	0.182		0.607	

Note 1: * $p < .05$; *** $p < .001$.

Note 2: "Female" is the reference group for gender, "Senior" is the reference group for grade, and "Rural" is the reference group for place of origin

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

In this study, the "gender" of painting majors in Liaoning Province of China has no significant difference in family capital. The findings demonstrate that parental investment in the allocation and support of family resources is essentially the same for boys and girls, indicating that the importance that families place on child development is not limited by gender [40].

In this study, the "grade" of painting majors in Liaoning Province of China has no significant difference in family capital. The results of this study prove that family capital has continuity and stability in students' education, and does not change significantly depending on grade differences. The economic, cultural and social capital provided by families in the process of children's education is a long-term and stable investment, and will not change significantly depending on the change of children's grade [41].

In this study, there are significant differences in family capital in the "origin" of painting majors in Liaoning Province, China. The main reasons for this result are as follows: First, urban areas usually have a higher level of economic development, a higher income, and a relatively good family economic situation. Urban families can provide more financial resources to support their children's education and artistic development, such as purchasing painting materials and paying for training courses. However, the economic development of rural areas is relatively backward, residents' income is generally low, and families' economic support ability is relatively limited [42]. Second, urban areas have easier access to various extracurricular training courses and art education resources to further enhance students' cultural capital. In contrast, schools in rural areas are relatively short of educational resources, with low levels of educational facilities and teachers, limited opportunities for students to receive quality education, and relatively little accumulation of cultural capital [43]. Third, the cultural atmosphere of rural families is relatively weak, and parents generally have low educational concepts and cultural level, less support for children's cultural and artistic education, and relatively insufficient accumulation of cultural capital [44].

According to the results of quantitative research, it can be seen that the family capital of painting students in Liaoning Province of China has a significant positive impact on career maturity. Studies have shown that the higher the student's family capital, the higher the career maturity. The results of this study prove that there is a significant positive correlation between family capital and career maturity. Family capital includes economic capital, cultural capital and social capital, which together provide students with abundant resources and support to help students achieve better results in career selection and development. Economic capital refers to the economic status of the family, cultural capital refers to the cultural background and educational level of the family, and social capital includes the family's interpersonal network and social relations [45]. Families with sufficient economic capital can provide students with more learning and training opportunities, families with rich cultural capital can cultivate students' broader interests and professional knowledge, and families with strong social capital can provide students with more career guidance and networking resources. Therefore, students with higher family capital will enjoy more educational resources and social support during their growth, and thus show higher maturity and self-confidence in career planning and decision-making.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study systematically analyzed the influence of family capital on vocational maturity of painting majors in Liaoning Province, China, and verified the role of family economic capital, family cultural capital and family social capital in the development of students' vocational maturity through questionnaire survey. According to the analysis results, there are significant differences in career maturity among painting majors in Liaoning Province, China, with different genders and grades. There are significant differences in family capital and career maturity among painting majors in Liaoning Province of China. Family capital has a significant positive influence on career maturity of painting students in Liaoning Province. Through this comprehensive analysis, the understanding of career maturity is deepened, and it also provides a solid theoretical basis for further exploring the differences of career development and social mobility among different social classes in the future. However, there are still some research limitations in the study. The following are the specific research limitations and relevant suggestions for future research.

This study focuses on career maturity from the perspective of students and neglects the perspectives of teachers and parents. The perspectives and experiences of teachers and parents, as important components of the education system and support system, also have a significant impact on students' career maturity. Students receive guidance and advice from teachers in school and influence and support from parents at home, both of which play an important role in the development of students' career maturity. In addition, this study, using students majoring in painting in Liaoning Province, China, as a sample, has some professional limitations and may not fully represent the situation of students in other majors. Painting majors are highly artistic and specific and may be significantly different from other majors. Therefore, the limitations of the specialization may lead to restrictions on the generalization and application of the results and make it difficult to achieve the same results in different contexts.

Therefore, the scope of research subjects should be expanded in future studies to include the perspectives of teachers and parents to gain a comprehensive understanding of the multiple factors affecting students' vocational maturity. Interviews and questionnaires with teachers and parents can also be used to gain insights into their confusion and needs in vocational education, providing data support for the development of more effective educational policies and family support strategies. In addition, it is necessary to expand the scope of sample selection by choosing students from different majors to comparatively analyze the influencing factors of career maturity in different professional contexts. Specific methods may include a multi-major cross-sectional comparative study and a longitudinal follow-up study.

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